

Effective Management Of Secondary Education: Key To National Integration And Economy Recovery In Nigeria

John, Iibi & Onuoha, Anne Nyegierefaka

**Department Of Educational Management
Rivers State University Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Email: iibi.john@ust.edu.ng/Phone No: 09035124770**

ABSTRACT

Education has continually been identified as a vital tool for social, economic and political development; an instrument that propels changes in a society, and a catalyst for nation building. It is viewed as the highest source of empowerment an individual can acquire, as it teaches exhibition of desirable behaviour and makes people aware of their rights, privileges and obligations. This paper examined the effective management of secondary education as a key for national integration and economic recovery. To achieve this, the concept of secondary education, management of secondary education, national integration, economic recovery and the effective management of secondary education as a key to national integration were discussed. The paper established that secondary education is a form of formal education that is aimed at preparing people for useful living in the society; a means of changing people's life, give better exposure, improve people's experience and receptiveness to new ideas, knowledge, concepts, values and customs; and a force that manipulates human intelligence and abilities that results towards better knowledge acquisition, values altitudinal change and skilled oriented activities. Given the benefits of secondary education in any society, the paper advocates that the management of secondary education should be more effective ensuring that the aims of secondary education are achieved which will enhance the attainment of national integration and economic recovery.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Economic recovery National Integration, Management of Secondary Education.

INTRODUCTION

From ancient times to date, education has continually played several roles in our society. Different scholars have described education in various ways, Cornford (1968) in Ihenetu and Onyekwelu (2017) observed that Plato of ancient Greece identified education as a potent instrument that was necessary for the production of a perfect society .In another view Nyerere (1967) also in Ihenetu and Onyekwelu (2017) describe education as an instrument that can be used for the reinforcement of the ideals of a society, describing education as a tool that comprehends all influences of future citizens towards building the complete man. Similarly, Nwadiani (2000) in Onuoha and Agabi (2021) acclaimed education as a magic wand for the solution to the problems that plague mankind.

In the world today, every nation including Nigeria has come to understand that formal education stands as a vibrant instrument in the training and developing of individuals. Udo and Uyanga (2023) adds that formal education most especially secondary education has the ability of elevating the level of man's knowledge and skills required for building appropriate human relationships. Secondary education in Nigeria is a bridge linking primary and tertiary education which is of strategic importance in harnessing various opportunities. Secondary education by means of its objectives prepares youths for future responsibility by building a strong, united and

economically viable nation (Onuoha & Agabi, 2021) leading to national integration and development. Hence, a contemporary Nigeria good secondary education certification had been an acceptable qualification for various jobs in the military, industries, factories and offices

It was observed by Udie (2007) in Udo and Uyanga (2023) that national unity and integration in Nigeria has become an issue of public concern that is often treated as part of Nigeria's national goals which the education system has been positioned as an instrument to tackle. National integration which also means national unity, is a term that is used to define when the citizens of a country see themselves as having a common identity, regard themselves as one and work together towards the development of their country irrespective of class, ethnicity, religion, political, etc, differences (Pearl, 2018).

National integration has been devised as a strategy that has to do with the alteration in the relationship between people and with respect to the flow of interactions and co-existence whereby citizens of a country find their places within a community without reference to their ethnic, religious, class or political groups. National integration is aimed at the creation of a common nationhood as well as structures and institutions necessary for national development. National integration is focused at fusing various forms of groups into one, a process that attempts to eliminate the presence of small nationalities with the feeling of oneness; achievable only through inculcating and assimilating the spirit of oneness in all individuals (Farinde, 2016).

Nigeria just like many other countries of the world strive for an integrated nation that is devoid of cultural, religious, political and tribal conflicts that keeps destroying countries all over the world. Nigeria economy has officially. This paper on the effective management of secondary education: key to national integration in Nigeria intends to explore the concepts of secondary education and national integration thereby providing a benchmark that views secondary education as the avenue were Nigeria's national integration can be structured on.

Conceptual Clarification

Source: Self Developed

Secondary Education

The Nigerian educational system is made up of four educational levels made up of: Early childhood centers, primary education, secondary education and tertiary education. Early childhood centers also referred to pre-school is designed for children between the ages of 0-4 years. This is a critical stage in the life of children given that it is the period where physical, cognitive and psychosocial development takes place, as such great concern is given to their care, nutrition and stimulation for best cognitive and physical development.

The second level of education is primary education comprising of six years for children between the ages of 6-12 years. This level is divided into junior primary (1-3) and senior primary (4-6). This level of education is made compulsory and free by the federal government with objectives which include: inculcating literacy, numeracy and an ability to communicate with people; the promotion of patriotism, fairness, understanding and national unity; laying a basis for scientific, critical and reflective thoughts, being able to instill moral norms and values; and to provide avenues where the child can develop manipulative skills so as to be able to well in the society (FRN, 2014).

Secondary education is the third educational level which is made up of students between the ages of 11-16 also made up of two sections, junior secondary comprising of JS 1-3 and Senior secondary comprising of SS 1-3. Junior secondary education is part of primary education also classified as Universal Basic Education which is a compulsory, free and basic education offered to Nigeria children for nine years after which if their parents can't afford their education the students' may withdraw from formal education. On the other hand, senior secondary education is the level of education that prepares students for tertiary education. In that vein, students are classified into different sub groups of subjects that determine their future careers and a nurturing period for the students in their desired areas of qualification.

Secondary education serves as the vital link between primary and tertiary education and also a gateway to the labour market for those who may not wish to continue into tertiary education (Nsude 2015). Abraham and Amaechina (2011) opines that secondary education is the level of education where children are exposed to a wider world where their minds are sharpened for further academic work, incorporated into political, economic and social competences, as well as helped to raise their intelligence. The importance of secondary education in educational system cannot be overemphasized. It is a medium between the primary and tertiary, and it prepares them for work. It affords the child the opportunity to acquire additional knowledge, skills, and qualities beyond the primary level. The acquisition of the secondary education in Nigeria was as a result of education provided at the primary level has proven to be insufficient for a child to acquire permanent literacy, communicative, and numeracy skills expected from them at the end of the training (John & Agabi, 2019).

In the view of Aggarwal (2008) as cited in Nsude (2015) secondary education is the period where students get into the responsibilities of life and take up vocations, which is why the curriculum is designed to not only provide academic studies but also vocational, technical, and entrepreneurial education, as well as foster patriotism and security education with emphases on the common ties, in spite of our diversity. The basic function of secondary education system in Nigeria is to prepare students for useful living within society and for higher education. The objectives of secondary education, according to the National Policy on Education (2014) include:

1. The provision of all primary school learners with the opportunity for higher education, irrespective of sex, social status, religious, or ethnic background.
2. The availability of a diversified curriculum that is prepared to offer educational differences in talents, opportunities, and future roles.
3. Providing trained manpower in applied science, technology, and commerce at sub-professional grades.
4. The development and promotion of Nigerian language, art, and culture in the context of its cultural heritage.
5. Inspiring students with a desire for self-improvement towards attaining excellence.
6. Fostering national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity.
7. Raising a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals, and live as good citizens of the Country.

8. The provision of technical knowledge and vocational skills for students' that are necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial, and economic development.

The challenges of secondary education according to Nemezuchioma, Ogbonna and Chinakanwosu (2021) comprise of insufficient funding of the sector, lack/inadequate necessary school infrastructure, instructional materials and methodologies, irregular school inspection and teacher supervision, unavailable guidance and counselling services for staff and students, inadequate qualified staff, inexperienced and qualified school administrators, etc.

Management of Secondary Education in Nigeria

Secondary education plays important roles in the actualization of making an individual self-reliant and developing the nation. Hence, over the years, many secondary schools were opened and the existing ones were expanded in availability of infrastructure, so as to provide the formal education needed for the secondary school going age. Management of secondary schools has involuntarily come under focus by stake holders of education as the bane of pragmatic secondary school education. Parents, students and other stakeholders may only maintain a stance of simulated innocence but could also be blamed in their respective concerns.

The management of secondary education is concerned with the planning and formation of educational policies or programmes in line with its objectives towards achieving educational goals. Management of secondary education involves planning, organising, staffing, directing, controlling, coordinating, and budgeting. Agabi (2018) views the management of secondary education as the process that entails the effective utilization of human and material resources through the functions of positive planning, organising, directing, leading, coordinating, and controlling to achieve positive educational outcomes.

Onuoha and Agabi (2021) adds that the management of secondary education has to do with strategizing, planning, organising, running, and supervising the entire process of teaching and learning processes that take place at secondary school level. According to Amadi (2014), the management of secondary education in Nigeria is coordinated by the Ministry of Education at both the national and federal levels. The Federal Ministry of Education is a federal agency saddled with the responsibility of regulating both federal and state secondary schools. However, the State Ministries of Education are specifically in charge of state-owned public secondary schools as well as private secondary schools. The vision of both the Federal and State Ministries of Education intervention and regulatory agencies is to promote a uniform, qualitative and functional secondary education in Nigeria.

Another role of the Federal Ministry of Education is to function as a coordinating and monitoring agency that is saddled with the responsibility to progressively improve the educational capacity of states, local government agencies, and communities in the provision of unfiltered access to high-quality and functional secondary education in Nigeria. Secondary education programmes in Nigeria are implemented through close collaborative partnerships between federal and state post-primary school management boards and secondary education stakeholders at all levels.

Also important in the management of secondary education in Nigeria are the various school heads (principals). The management of secondary schools are expected to work in collaboration with parents, learners, environments, and other stakeholders within their communities. They are expected to bridge the gap between the government and the people at the grassroots/communities whilst providing secondary education. Therefore, as educational professionals, the management of secondary education are expected to plan, organize, direct and coordinate all educational activities of the State and students. The principal who is the chief administrator of secondary schools is expected to effectively assign duties to teaching and non-teaching staff, ensuring to supervise them towards achieving the objectives of secondary education.

Onuoha and Agabi (2021) opine the challenges in the management of secondary education in Nigeria to include: Inadequate funding, instability of teachers in the teaching profession, politicization of the education system, power conflict in the management of education, indiscipline in the educator sector, etc. In another view, Adeniran (2020) identified the challenges of the management of secondary education to include: Poor implementation of government policies, poor funding of education sector, corruption and mismanagement of resources, lack of qualified teachers, inadequate facilities and poor working conditions and faulty training received by students. They suggested solutions to the challenges of management of secondary education to

include: adequate teacher education training with adequate provision of resources with re-introducing of Teacher Colleges, quality assurance in terms of class size, number of teachers and instructional materials, implementation of Schools Management Committees (SMCs), adequate budgetary provision, employment of professional staff, empowerment approach to education, provision of child friendly and teacher friendly school environment, review of school curricula for promoting relevant learning and extra curricula activities, admission of students to schools base on merit not political ground and special salary for teachers should be provided.

Concept of National Integration in Nigeria

The definition of integration according to the dictionary is the quality of being entire and undivided, protecting national sovereignty and geographical integrity. Coleman and Rotberg (1964) in Alozie (2018) define national integration as the progressive reduction of cultural and regional tensions and discontinuities in the process of creating a homogeneous political community. Similarly, Ogunjenite (1978) also in Alozie (2018) identify national integration as the building of nation states out of desperate socio-economic, religious and ethnic geographical elements.

Akpati (2015) defines integration as a resocialisation process into the symbols of the new large community to create people in the sense of those who, in the words of Karl Dentsch, can be described to have learned to communicate with each other well beyond the mere interchange of goods and services. Balewa (1957) still in Akpati (2015) view national integration as the collective orientation of members of a society towards the nation and its society in manner that micro-loyalties are not allowed to destroy the continued existence of the nation and its objectives, goals and ideals. To Weiner (1967) as cited in Alozie (2018) national integration refers to a situation of creating a sense of territorial nationality whereby subordinate parochial loyalties are eliminated and set aside so as to enjoy oneness. Weiner and Laparambola (1969) also in Alozie (2018) identify national integration as the involvement of an amalgamation of disparate social, economic, religious, ethnic and geographic elements into a single nation state.

In defining national integration, Hogan (2006) as cited in Pearl (2018) defines national integration as the uniting of formerly separate groups into one united group with the cancellation of any previous social or cultural group differences as well as the cancellation of separate group identifications thereby building a united group. Enaruna (2014) adds that national integration implies that the capacity of a government to control the territory under its jurisdiction as well as the set of popular attitudes of its citizens towards the nation define national integration which is focused on loyalty, allegiance, and intelligence to place the nation above local and parochial concerns.

Alozie (2018) opines that national integration is aimed at fostering unity, fairness, cooperation, consensus building and non-violent mechanisms for conflict resolutions which is geared towards loyalty and nation building. He further identified the characteristics of national integration to include:

1. A society that has control over the use of the means of violence.
2. Having a Centre of decision making that is capable of effecting the allocation of resources and rewards.
3. Having a dominant focus of political identification for a large majority of politically aware citizens.
4. When various units of develop a system for the resolution of social problems without resorting to violence or physical force.

Enaruna (2014) posits that national integration is geared towards the promotion and emergence of peace by means of breaking down cultural and regional divides towards the process of building a united nation. National integration involves setting aside significant disparities while still preserving each group's own identity in order to bring them together under a single identity. The efforts of national integration are aimed towards wielding together a pluralistic society in order to enhance development without necessarily jeopardizing ethnic identity. Nemezuchioma, et al. (2021) adds that national integration is actualized when members of a State see themselves as one, treat one another fairly and work together co-operatively and freely agree to, and do resolve their differences peacefully in the overall interest of the nation and its people.

Akpati (2015) identifies the challenges of national integration in Nigeria to comprise of the issue of ethnic diversity, the issue of structural imbalance among states and communities, nepotism among citizens and

political leaders, inappropriate revenue allocation and sharing method, activities of some religious and ethnic fanatics who are loyal to members of their religion and communities, political representation in the various arms of government, etc.

Economic Recovery

Economic recovery refers to the process of rebuilding and revitalizing an economy after a period of decline, recession, or crisis (Blanchard, 2018). It involves implementing policies and strategies to stimulate economic growth, create jobs, and increase prosperity (Romer, 2019). Gross domestic product (GDP) grows normally during an economic recovery, incomes rise, and unemployment falls as the economy rebounds. The economy undergoes a process of adaptation and adjustment to new conditions, factors that triggered the recession in the first place and the new policies and rules implemented by governments and central banks in response to the recession are included during an economic recovery. The factors of production and other resources that were sunk into the failed businesses during the recession are re-deployed in new ventures as unemployed workers find new jobs and failed businesses are bought from the owners. Recovery is an economy healing itself from the damage done, and it sets the stage for a new expansion (Elisha & Mmom, 2022).

An economic recovery occurs after a recession as the economy adjusts and recovers some of the gains lost during the recession. The economy then eventually transitions to a true expansion when growth accelerates and GDP starts moving toward a new peak. Not every period of slow growth or even contraction is severe enough to be designated as a recession. In the United States, the most common rule of thumb for a recession is if there are two consecutive quarters of negative GDP growth (The National Bureau of Economic Research, 2021; Kleemans & Thornton, 2021).

Economic recovery, while still on evolving concept, set of practices and the need for greater coherence, is increasingly understood as an approach focused on enabling government and communities to rebuild and economically recover from war and other crises, though doing so in new and transformative ways can facilitate the consolidation of peace (Elisha & Mmom, 2022). Economic recovery efforts should catalyze development activities. They should build upon and maximize the utility of earlier humanitarian efforts, and lay foundations for sustainable and longer-term development that can bring lasting transformation of the societal economic structures that were part and parcel of the conflict era.

According to Nigerian national planning commission (2017), economic recovery can be achieved by:

1. Diversifying the economy beyond oil exports.
2. Investing in infrastructure
3. Promoting agriculture and manufacturing
4. Encouraging foreign investment
5. Improving governance and reducing corruption

LITERATURE REVIEW

Different studies have affirmed the importance of education most especially secondary education: Adeniran (2018) in a study on the effective management of secondary education as a tool for socio-economic and political emancipation in Nigeria, affirmed that secondary education is a means of achieving economic and political emancipation. Similarly, Nemezuchioma, et. al. (2021) examined sustaining national integration and development in Nigeria through secondary education and discovered that secondary education can actually be used to sustain national integration. Ossai (2023) investigated the management of secondary education in Nigeria for national cohesion and actually saw secondary education as a tool. Alozie (2018) explored communal conflicts and challenges for national integration in Nigeria in the 21st century and discovered that education has a crucial role to play. Ihenetu and Onyekwelu (2012) examined education as a melting pot of cultures: The integrative function and the results showed that education had a role in melting cultures for national unity. Udo and Uyanga (2023) studied education system and preservation of culture for national unity and integration in Nigeria: Prospects and challenges and in their study discovered that education.

Obanya (2009) cited in Nsude (2015) opines that the ability of learners to use knowledge, skills, competences, values, and attitudes acquired at this educational level to desire, seek, recognise, and utilize every opportunity

available to them to build integration and create wealth for themselves and others is one of the basics of secondary education. As this tool will enable them to enhance the integration of various groups into one nation, thereby reinforces value systems, and better positioning them to realize their different goals if properly managed. Hence for secondary education to actually achieve its predetermined goals and objectives towards becoming an instrument for fostering national integration in Nigeria, it must be effectively managed.

Different studies have been carried out by educational scholars to explain Economic recovery Elisha and Mmom (2022) carried out a study on leadership approaches in mitigating substantial risk for economy recovery in Nigeria fourth republic. The paper examined leadership approaches in mitigating substantial risk for economy recovery in Nigeria Fourth Republic. The paper conceptualized leadership and several substantial risk facing the country like; social, ethnic and religious tensions, institutional weaknesses, political risk environment, inconsistent public regulations and corruption that also hinder economy recovery. The paper further revealed the several leadership approaches in mitigating substantial risk for economy recovery, such as; restoring economics, diversifying supply chain/mainstay, combating corrupting, economic challenges for marginalized group and meeting the moment leadership approaches. The paper concluded that economic recovery is seen as a lesser priority in peace consolidation than security/political reform, and when support has resumed through a functional leadership approaches for economic recovery under substantial risk and war-torn countries, there is hope for stable developing countries. A country with substantial risk, government can employ restoring economics, diversifying supply chain/mainstay, combating corrupting, economic challenges for marginalized group and meeting the moment leadership approaches to help recover its economy. The paper suggested that government need to reduce cost of governance and rebalance their sovereign debt portfolio maturities while stimulating growth; as well as take an active role in designing and enforcing economic policies to address various problems that pure market forces cannot, such as externalities and the absence of risk markets.

Inoykwe (2018), also wrote on economic recovery and growth plan and nation building in Nigeria: matters arising. He said that the economic recession experienced by Nigeria between 2016 and 2017 constrained government's effort at generating revenue and implementing national development plans. In order to remedy the situation, the Buhari government introduced the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) in 2017 as a policy option. The ERGP is designed to diversify the economy, restore economic growth, create jobs, empower the youths, develop the human capital and infrastructure, improved business environment and bring about technological growth. But the success of the ERGP is hinged on the ability of the Buhari led All Progressive Congress government to muster the political will and implement the ERGP in the midst of corruption, predatory and alienated political culture and the symbolic approach to implementing development policies and programmes in Nigeria. Making deductions from the primary and secondary data used analytical variables the paper concluded that Nigeria needs strongmen, strong institutions, and good political culture for the ERGP to succeed. The apprehension that the predatory and alienated political culture and political interest and social apathy may undermine the successful implementation of the ERGP is justifiable. The checklist of solutions provided requires changes in the ethical, social and political orientation of governance by stakeholders for the ERGP to yield optimal results.

This paper on the effective management of secondary education: key to national integration in Nigeria and economic recovery intends to explore the concepts of secondary education and national integration thereby providing a benchmark that views secondary education as the avenue were Nigeria's national integration can be structured on.

In order to recovery an economy, government can encourage citizens spending with policy responses and also stimulate investments particularly foreign direct investments and inflow of strategic funds for infrastructure investment and development to assist in the reversal of the trend. As a people, they must invest in capital expenditure expenses and strategic infrastructure to revamp the economy. More so, to cushion the effect of recession, harmonisation of both fiscal and monetary policy is essential. The economic stimulatory measures targeted at taxpayers to save their businesses and investments from collapse should be strengthened by the government. Perhaps, the government might need to consider more accelerated policy reforms and pragmatic

palliatives such as Investor confidence supports, Growth accelerates back to trend, social and fiscal policy palliatives, concessions on import trades, duties, and port charges waiver to reduce the value chain disruption. Effectiveness is accomplished by achieving stated objectives; therefore, the effective management of secondary education implies that secondary education should be managed towards producing successful results in secondary education. This follows that effective management of secondary education means when the management of secondary education apply effective methods that are geared into achieving educational goals at this educational level.

Effective Management of Secondary Education as a Key to National Integration in Nigeria and Economic Recovery

The above aims and objectives of secondary education make it clear that the future and unity of any nation depend largely on the quality of education given at this educational level as it provides its citizens with the basics of living with yourself and with others in your society. Since the quality of education received at this level is vital, there is a need to effectively manage secondary education for national integration and economic recovery. In fact, after going through secondary education, learners are expected to be able to contribute effectively and productively to life's activities for themselves, the society and the national at large.

Successive Nigeria governments have attempted, with varying degrees of success, to address the problem of lack of national integration and the tendency towards primordial attachments of citizens through deliberate policies and programmes including the use of creation of more states, the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme, the Unity Schools, the Federal Character Principle among others (Nsude, 2015). In spite of all the efforts of the government, the challenge of unity and national integration has persisted. Farinde (2016) views the reason for the division among citizens as the inability of Nigerian politicians and elites to steadily provide good governance; harness the many benefits of diverse ethnic, religious and economic groups as a source of strength rather than weakness. It is really sad to note that, after more than 100 years of statehood and sixty-four years of political independence, the search for national integration, security, stability, peace, order and development have continued to remain elusive.

Secondary education plays a critical role in shaping the future of any nation, and Nigeria is no exception. With over 200 million people and over 400 ethnic groups, Nigeria faces significant challenges in ensuring national integration and economic recovery. One of the key solutions to these challenges lies in effective management of secondary education. Effective management of secondary education in Nigeria can contribute to national integration and economic recovery in several ways according to Amuwo (2014):

1. By providing a common curriculum that emphasizes national values and unity, secondary education can help to break down ethnic and regional barriers, fostering a sense of national identity and cohesion.
2. Investing in quality education can attract foreign investment, as companies are more likely to invest in countries with a skilled and educated workforce. This investment can in turn lead to economic growth and stability.

CONCLUSION

Unarguably, education is paramount to the development of individual's propensity to trust and be tolerant, which is a tool for the achievement of national integration. Education, and indeed, secondary education in particular, has a set of rules and standards that should be transmitted to learners to prepare them for the achievement of the goals of secondary education. Secondary education by virtue of its position in the Nigerian education system is of strategic importance to the education system. This follows that if secondary education is effectively managed it can serve as a key to Nigeria's national integration by emphasizing on those values that unites us as a people and citizens of this great nation and ensuring the smooth transmission of these values. It is important to also note that the principals, who are the major stakeholders in secondary education and who also interface with parents, learners, environments, and other stakeholders, should therefore process certain necessary leadership and administrative skills in ensuring that there is effectiveness in the management of secondary education if national integration is to be obtained.

SUGGESTIONS

For national integration and recovery to be achieved through secondary school there is urgent need for the following activities:

1. To address the state of school facilities in secondary schools.
2. To ensure the employment of professionally qualified teaching and non-teaching staff should not be recruited into the profession.
3. Proper supervision and quality control should be put in place to ensure that secondary school curriculum is implemented effectively.
4. There is need for proper funding of the secondary education system.
5. Guidance and counseling departments should be made available in all schools to help youths grow into useful citizens.
6. Periodic review of secondary school curriculum must be ensured to make it responsive to contemporary social, political and economic challenges.
7. Learning outcomes should not only address academic performance but should also be directed towards the full development of human potential and to ensure that education is a life-long process in all social contexts (family, school, workplace, and community).
8. Educational institutions are not only avenues for teaching and learning but can also be centres of support for learners and educators to promote referrals to school services.
9. Co-curriculum activities should be strengthened and monitored, such as those involving dialogues that promote intellectual understanding.

REFERENCES

- Adeniran, O. S. (2020). Effective management of secondary education as a tool for socio-economic and political emancipation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Contemporary Education Research*, 19(8), 117-130.
- Agabi, C. O. (2018). Building the gap between secondary and tertiary education. *African Social and Educational Journal*, 7(2), 123-138.
- Akpati, M. (2015). *Nigeria: The tragedy of unity in diversity*. In *African Herald Express* (That The Truth May Prevail) March 2, 2015. Retrieved from www.africanheraldexpress.com
- Alozie, C. C. (2018). Communal conflicts and challenges of national integration in Nigeria in the 21st century. *African Social and Educational Journal*, 7(2), 47-61.
- Amuwo, D. (2014). Education and National Integration in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges. *Ibadan Journal of Humanistic Studies*, 11(2), 87-104.
- Blanchard, O. J. (2018). Should we reject the Natural Rate Hypothesis? *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 32(1), 97-120.
- Elisha, O. D., & Mmom, C. P. C. (2022). Leadership approaches in mitigating substantial risk for economy recovery in Nigeria's fourth republic. Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Institutional Leadership and Capacity Building in Africa ICILCB2020 (1-11). ICILCB2022 held on the 26th-29th September 2022 at University of Delta, Agbor, Nigeria.
- Hoque, T. (2023). National integration among students in the secondary school. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 4(2), 50-53.
- Ihenetu, K. A. & Onyekwelu, S. (2012). Education as a melting pot of cultures: The integrative function. *Nigeria Journal of Professional teachers*, 5, 55-59.
- John, I. & Agabi, C. O. (2019). Managing secondary education for quality: A case for improving quality of labour supply in a developing economy. *Nigerian Journal for Educational Administration and Planning (NJEAP)* 19(5) 1-15, www.nacap.org.ng
- Kleemans, M., & Thornton, R. L. (2021). Who belongs? The determinants of selective membership into the national bureau of economic research. In *AEA Papers and Proceedings*, 111 (117-122)

- Nemezuchioma, P., Ogbonna, E. G. & Chinakanwosu, J. (2021). Sustaining national integration and development in Nigeria through secondary education. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences (IJHSS)*, 10(1), 161–170
- Nigerian national planning commission (2017). Economic recovery and growth plan (ERGP) 2017-2020.
- Nsudo, A. O. (2015). Constraints to entrepreneurial education as perceived by secondary school principals in Enugu State. Unpublished Thesis. Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT) Enugu
- Onuoha, A. N. & Agabi, C. O. (2021). Teacher wastage in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *ICRAW International Journal of Education and Social Research*, 8(1), 33-49.
- Ossai, A. G. (2023). Managing Secondary Education in Nigeria for National Cohesion. *Journal Ilmu Sosiologi Dialektika Kontemporer*, 11(2), 2303-2324.
- Ozochi, C. (2010). Introduction to Adult Education Principals and Applications. Cecta Nigeria Limited.
- Pearl, P. (2018). *Ten Problems of Nigeria National Integration and Possible Solutions*: InfoGuide Nigeria.
- Peretomode, V. F. (2012). *Introduction to educational administration, planning and supervision*. Joja Educational Research and Publishers
- Romer, D. (2019). *Advanced macroeconomics* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- The national bureau of economic research (2021). *What's a recession: anyway*. NBER.
- Udo, E. E. & Uyanga, U. D. (2023). Education system and preservation of culture for national unity and integration in Nigeria: Prospects and challenges. In Musa, C. N., Ekwukoma, V. & Osagiobare, O. E. (Eds). *Perspectives on issues in education: Charting the course for sustainable development in Nigeria* (344-358). Publication of the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, University of Benin.